

Influence of Classroom Management Strategies on Students Learning

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Abstract

Classroom management plays a leading role in uplifting teaching and learning process. It helps in producing a conducive learning environment where students can learn with ease and perform better academically. Proper utilization of classroom management strategies in the classrooms enhances the learning outcomes of students. The study was a descriptive type survey in nature, so a self-developed questionnaire was used to collect the required information from the respondents. The population of the study was comprised of 3702 female teachers of public girls' secondary schools of Sahiwal division. The simple random technique was adopted to select 160 teachers from the target population. The results of the study show that classroom management strategies enhanced students' learning and classroom management strategies have a positive effect on improving students' learning. It was concluded that classroom management strategies have a great effect on the betterment of the classroom environment. It was further recommended that teachers might be provided in-service training for further proper utilization of classroom management strategies to improve students' learning.

Keywords: Classroom Management, Learning environment, Strategies, Students learning, Learning Outcomes.

Introduction

A classroom is a room or a learning place where children and adults both get an education. Classrooms are present in all educational institutions. The classroom provides a place where learning can take place without outside interruptions. Classroom management can be defined as a collection of organizational objective focused on using time sensibly to increase learning and on sustaining a secure classroom atmosphere that is favorable to student learning. Classroom management strategies is a wide variety of techniques and skills that enable teachers to keep students orderly, organized, attentive, focused on the task and academically productive during class. Students' learning is the overall course of getting or perceiving new and modifying previous knowledge, skill behaviors, and values.

Dudhe (2014) Education is a mean of development. In the respective society classification of society depends upon the status of education. In today's global age developed countries always sustain the suitable pathway of education. Technical, professional, non-profession, practical and business education gives the backbone to the nation. If people are literate, they will be conscious of social issues and problems in the country. Skillful and trained persons are the pillars to grow the society with the aid of various parameters — faculty training course program and inspiration criteria also important for the betterment of education in society. Awareness and attentiveness about basic education are essential for development in society. Overpopulation, child labor, poverty, women exploitation alcoholism, etc. are the major social evils interrelated with the education system. Basic and standard education can solve and sort out these problems efficiently.

For human and economic development education is a vital investment and it is influenced by the atmosphere in which it exists. Changes in the labor market, technology, and general global environment, all need policy responses. The education system is affected by traditions, culture, and faith. The social, political and legislative structures also invade on the effectiveness of the education system. (Govt. of Punjab, 2009) education is the road to development of the nation. It develops a sense of accountability among the people. Education helps people to realize their duties and to achieve their national and social rights.

Education is a constant process and plays an important role in the individual's life. Education aims at rising all aspects of individual's character such as social, spiritual, physical, mental, cultural and emotional so that he

can take part in the development of his own self, his nation, and society. Education is a continuous process as the society changes; the role of education also changes. During the process of evolution, education conveyed diverse meaning according to conditions (Tiwari & Panwari, 2014).

The study is an effort to explore the effects of teachers' classroom management on students' learning. Teachers' appropriate use of classroom management strategies is a source that enhances the learning of students within the classroom. We know that classroom management is a key factor that can directly affect students' achievements. So it is important to find out the effect of classroom management strategies in order to enhance students learning abilities. With the help of this study, the researcher had tried to find out classroom management strategies utilized in schools by different teachers and their consequences on student learning.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out teachers' classroom management strategies.
2. To identify the effects of classroom management strategies on students' learning.
3. To make a comparison of teachers' classroom management strategies.

Research Questions

1. What are the classroom management strategies?
2. How classroom management strategies affect students' learning?
3. Which are the different classroom management strategies used by teachers?

The significance of the Study

Quality education is the main aspect for uplifting standards of education in the country. This can only be attained by proper use of classroom management strategies along with stipulation of updated professional training to teachers and their school heads. This study is very important as it provides fruitful findings to teachers, heads, stakeholders, policymakers, government officials and for upcoming teachers. The study will be helpful to heads of schools at the secondary level to take necessary steps at their disposal to improve the quality of education in their respective institutions. This study is also supportive of teaching force at all levels especially at the secondary level for improving their methods of teaching and classroom management. The study has significant value for researchers to carry out further research in this particular area since it offers a broader view of the magnitude of in- service training for the civilizing professional capability of teachers.

Methods and Procedure of the Study

The study was descriptive in nature. The survey technique was used to collect data for the study. All the teachers (3702) of public secondary schools in the Sahiwal Division formed the population of the study. The researcher used the simple random sampling technique for the selection of a sample of the study. 160 teachers were chosen from Sahiwal division, 12 schools from each District, Sahiwal, Okara, and Pakpattan respectively. Schools were chosen through a simple random method. Keeping in view the classroom management strategies of a teacher at the secondary level the researcher designed a questionnaire as a tool to collect the views of teachers.

Review of the Related Literature

Management is an art of knowing what is to be done and seeing that it is done in the best possible manner. It comprises planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating and controlling. People forms groups to accomplish aims that could not be attained individually. Classroom management becomes an integral part of both teacher and students' success. It shows teacher performance in organizing, engaging and communicating students. In classroom setting schools and teachers create and maintain proper behaviors by management process. Teachers with practical vision, skills, strategies, and knowledge can manage a classroom successfully. Teachers must treat with surprising actions and students' misbehaviors with the help of effective classroom management strategies. Useful classroom organization and helpful classroom atmosphere production are critical goals for teachers (Katharina, 2015).

The term classroom management refers to decisions teachers take to assist the process of learning and to give the students all opportunities for learning. Classroom organization is not a gift that is bestowed upon teachers. It is a fact that some teachers manage the classroom easily. It is an ability that must be acquired in the teaching profession. To achieve proficiency this skill must be practiced. Classroom management requires a specific technique such as planning, communicating, organizing and mentoring. It demands a lot of initiatives, commitment, teachers' willingness to adjust actions and creative thinking (Abel, 2011).

Savage (2009) defines classroom management at two levels of management 1) prevention of problems and 2) responses when problems do occur. The main focus is on the prevention of problems which indicates that one of the key variables in classroom success is preventive, rather than reactive management technique. Teachers' ability to manage and organize classroom is key to success in teaching. Classroom management consists of a broad variety of techniques that teachers apply to keep students focused, organized, ordered and attentive on task. Classroom management is especially important as it is a central aspect of a teacher's practice and can have implications for student learning, engagement, and academic success. In classroom teachers create and maintain appropriate behavior by management. Its principles implemented at all grade level and across all subject areas. In the process of education, it is a complex exercise. Classroom management demands skills, talent, ability, and energy from teachers.

Ostrosky (2008) teacher plays an important role in developing a positive environment of the classroom. Inside the classrooms, teachers can make conditions in which learners feel secure and study how to work collectively as individuals. The role of the teachers is to increase learning and decrease disturbances by promoting feelings of trust, tolerance acceptance and cooperation among students.

Helpful teachers construct an environment of discipline cooperation and dependability equally for student and themselves. Teachers decide the atmosphere of the classroom. Teacher function is critical in controlling the students' behaviors — those teachers who plan sensibly overcome many classroom issues such as misbehaviors and disruptions between students (Riaz, 2009). The nature of the teacher plays a vital role in students learning (Aly, 2007). Teacher management technique will change the concept of the students about learning. Teachers' methodology to accomplish the classroom matters has great influence upon learning of the students. Closest interactions take place in the classroom between students and the teachers.

Classroom management fixes on the efficacy of teaching quality and learning of students. Competent teachers develop a supportive, sound and friendly environment. Classroom management strategies are implemented to enhance pro-social behavior and maximize student engagement (Emmer & Sabornie, 2015). Alfie Kohn (2015) classroom management skills are a critical part of teacher training. We need it to minimize students' misbehavior. Canter and Canter (2001) describe that classroom management firstly develop a highly supportive environment for learning secondly encourage a secure classroom environment so that students' motivation, interest, and contribution in the process of learning remain continued. Thirdly, students are permitted to set up relationships with teachers and other students. Behavioral management is a pre-planned intervention used to prevent misbehaviors. This type of management is utilized to prevent misbehavior before a response to misbehavior. Specifically, these aspects include establishing a reward arrangement, setting rules and provide opportunities for student participation. Pan (2010) examined classroom management in multicultural classrooms in urban schools in the United States of America (USA). Pan suggests that it is necessary for the teacher to incorporate students' home conditions in school to get a proactive approach. Pupils with Latin, black and Indian backgrounds are often expelled from the classrooms due to unacceptable behaviors

Lewis et al. (2008) good classroom management are necessary to develop a positive and constructive classroom environment. He also found that teacher aggression and punishment have no positive impact on pupils' behavior. Roache & Lewis (2011) teachers may not be conscious of how much pupils' behavior can be influenced by a teacher. They try to correct behaviors of pupils by using punishment together with aggressive

behaviors. Teachers show a lack of knowledge about the theoretical structure that can help them to manage the pupils.

Unal & Unal (2012) classroom management is a whole range of teacher attempt to control classroom activities such as learning, student behavior, and social interaction. It moves around students' and teachers' actions and attitudes that influence the behavior of student in the classroom. Efforts of teacher establish and sustain learning environment in the classroom both for teaching and learning. Previous researches have shown that the teachers' ability to organize instruction and managing classroom keys to success in teaching. Inappropriate use of classroom materials, feelings of insufficiency, stress noisy talk and walking uselessly are results of poor classroom management. Teachers those have no structured classroom management skills give negative student outcomes.

Use of classroom management strategies effectively can lower down the disruptions in classes. Classes, where effective management strategies are implemented, have higher achievement level higher than the students in classes where effective management strategies are not implemented. Classroom management includes post; maximize structure, review, monitoring and reinforcing expectations, and actively engaging students in noticeable ways, constant use of strategies to respond appropriate and inappropriate behaviors. (MacSuga & Simonsen, 2011)

Classroom management is an important element in the efficient learning process. Effective classroom management causes students to flourish in a constructive classroom environment. Classroom management is not intended to control absolutely or to build a docile, inert and totally obedient classroom and student. Effective classroom management is to retain students' interest, involvement, and motivation. Classroom management support and promote a secure classroom society so that students are permitted to build the relations required for learning to occur. Each student desires to feel comfortable sufficient to talk about their prior understanding exclusive of fear of being laugh at due to their misconceptions. Classroom management must consider and satisfy the developmental needs of students. It can be attained by developing an encouraging learning atmosphere, good ventilation, relaxing sound and stimulating sights (Mumtaz, 2010).

Merc & Subaşı (2015) Classroom management problems are the frustrating levels of sound in the classroom; Students do not participate in the lesson, naughty students and misbehaviors. Furthermore, teachers suffer another type of trouble in the classroom of gifted students. Such students talk without the permission of the teacher and are a source of annoyance for teacher and student. The boredom of the classroom increases when the teacher insists on student work all the time without any break or any change in activities and quietness all the time to keep students busy. Macias Sanchez (2015) excessive noise and heat, overcrowded classrooms, improper seating arrangements, Lack of sufficient resources, Students attitudes and language problem at primary and secondary schools, reluctance to participate in class and Lack of motivation and attention in class.

Sasidher et al. (2012) students those show disruptive behavior create problems in the classroom may also lead to low achievement. The teacher has to face many behavioral and academic problems regarding students in the classroom for example frequent absence, forgetting school tools, lack of attention, hyperactivity, unsuitable talk in the classroom vandalism, disobedience, aggressiveness and Lack of student motivation. Al-Amarat (2011) in general problems in the schools and classroom are vandalism, destruction of property, theft, failure in the school, poor study achievement, lack of facilities such as technology and equipment physical environment and the violence against student and teachers. The basic requirement in the educational process is classroom management and maintaining order inside the classroom. Inside the classroom management is an essential factor and it needs much time and effort. It is an important factor for teacher failure or success in his tasks (Marei & Mustafa 2009).

According to Latif et al., (2016), larger size classes, seeking attention from teachers, the unfairness of teachers, wish to gain power, teachers deprived of teaching skills, emotionally disturbed student problems and teacher's

style of classroom management are the major causes of students' disruptive behavior in the classroom. At last these behaviors and problems could be corrected through various educational programs presented by the school, paying attention to actions, which alleviate the school curriculum, increasing communication with parents to recognize the social, economic, health and mental status of the students and to encourage the social behavior and persuade the social life among them in afterward stages. The global disregard of the indecency by the teacher and the non- verbal intrusion through signals, gestures and approaching violent students' places may decline the behavioral problems. Classroom management strategies could be explained as methods and processes through which a teacher controls their classroom environment so that student learning prevails because student misbehavior is effectively minimized and redirected. Classroom management strategies are a critical part of teachers' achievement in creating a secure and efficient learning environment. Purpose of education is to grant a friendly and safe environment, so learning takes place. The teachers should be familiar with how to make use and pertain strategies that will permit and helps students to study (Zuckerman, 2007).

Organization in classroom plays an important role in student discipline. The classroom should be equipped with all facilities to make sure positive classroom conditions. The condition of physical facilities must be ensured as these are helpful to enhance the school's performance (Suleman & Hussain 2014). Physically arranged classroom not only provide easy access to the resources as well be able to use them. Organize the desks in a circle around the classroom. This type of organization will work better with smaller class sizes but can be used rarely in others. This strategy promotes public speaking and classroom discussion. It engages the students since all become a member of the similar group. Effective teachers strategically set furniture and equipment to increase learning and diminish distractions.

Table: 1 Classroom Management Criteria (a)

Statements	Area	SDA	DA	U	A	SA	Mean	SD
Classroom management is a critical part of effective instruction	Rural	3	11	6	42	19	3.77	1.702
	Urban	6	13	11	36	13	3.47	1.175
Classroom management helps teacher to teach effectively	Rural	3	11	6	41	19	3.87	1.07
	Urban	6	13	11	37	13	3.85	1.03
Student feel safe in conducive classroom environment	Rural	4	7	6	40	23	3.91	1.01
	Urban	3	8	7	42	20	3.83	1.091
Disciplined classroom helps teacher to teach well	Rural	3	7	6	42	22	3.89	1.08
	Urban	3	8	12	33	24	3.72	1.11
Teachers' motivation inspires students to work hard	Rural	3	8	8	41	20	3.83	1.03
	Urban	3	12	6	32	27	3.86	1.62
Classroom management is an efficient teacher.	Rural	2	14	6	36	22	3.77	1.10
	Urban	7	9	6	36	22	3.74	1.21
Well managed classrooms provide activity based teaching.	Rural	4	13	8	30	25	3.74	1.20
	Urban	2	13	9	39	17	3.70	1.06
Classroom management strategies play a vital role for teachers success	Rural	5	12	4	37	22	3.73	1.19
	Urban	2	14	7	37	20	3.75	1.10
Classroom management strategies provide a conducive environment for learning.	Rural	5	12	5	41	17	3.66	1.15
	Urban	2	9	12	38	19	3.77	1.02
Teacher use classroom management strategies to solve students' problems	Rural	6	13	5	39	17	3.58	1.20
	Urban	4	10	13	45	8	3.54	1.10
Effective classroom strategies help teachers to regulate students' attributes.	Rural	2	14	13	31	20	3.66	1.10
	Urban	1	16	5	37	21	3.75	1.10
Classroom management strategies used for effective Communication.	Rural	3	13	4	41	19	3.75	1.10
	Urban	5	14	10	33	18	3.56	1.20
Effective classroom strategies provide productive environment.	Rural	3	12	10	38	17	3.66	1
	Urban	3	13	9	37	18	3.68	1.11

The table 1 reflects that 61% rural & 49% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that classroom management is a critical part of effective instruction. The analysis of data showed that 60% rural & 50% urban

teachers were agreed with the statement that classroom management helps teacher teaches effectively. It was revealed from the results of the study that 63% rural & 62% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that students feel safe in a conducive classroom environment. It was shown from the data analysis that 64% rural & 57% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that disciplined classrooms help teachers to teach well. It was found from the respondents' response that 61% rural & 59% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that teachers' motivation inspires students to work hard. It was revealed from the results of the study that 58% rural & 58% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that classroom manager is an efficient teacher — the result of the study showed that 55% rural & 56% urban teachers were agreed with the statement which clearly indicates that well managed classrooms provide activity based teaching. It was shown from the respondents' response that 59% rural & 57% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement, that classroom management strategies play a vital role for teachers' success.

It was revealed from the respondents' response that 58% rural & 57% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that classroom management strategies provide a conducive environment for learning. It was found from the respondents' response 56% rural & 53% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that teacher use classroom management strategies to solve students' problems. It was indicated from the respondents' response that 51% rural & 58% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom strategies help teachers to regulate students' attributes. It was observed from the respondents' response 60% rural & 51% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that classroom management strategies used for effective Communication. It was indicated from the respondents' response that 55% rural & 55% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom strategies provide a productive environment.

Table: 2 Classroom Management Criteria (b)

Statements	Area	SDA	DA	U	A	SA	Mean	SD
Effective classroom management strategies reduce students' distraction.	Rural	6	8	8	41	17	3.69	1.36
	Urban	4	10	8	35	23	3.78	1.15
Communication is an important component of classroom management.	Rural	1	11	9	35	24	3.56	1.02
	Urban	6	12	10	35	17	3.56	1.20
Communication enables teachers to transfer knowledge.	Rural	6	6	11	45	12	3.6	1.06
	Urban	3	14	7	38	18	3.6	1.12
Effective classroom management enhances students' learning.	Rural	5	10	10	41	14	3.62	1.10
	Urban	7	10	6	40	17	3.62	1.21
Classroom management strategies used for monitoring.	Rural	6	10	5	36	23	3.54	1.21
	Urban	9	11	7	33	20	3.55	1.31
Good lesson planning is essential for effective teaching.	Rural	6	10	9	31	24	3.60	1.22
	Urban	6	9	14	32	19	3.60	1.19
Questioning is an important device of teaching.	Rural	6	6	8	41	19	3.77	1.121
	Urban	6	10	11	36	17	3.58	1.82
Classroom management is an appealing environment for students.	Rural	5	8	6	39	22	3.79	1.13
	Urban	6	10	8	33	23	3.72	1.22
Effective classroom management promotes students' relationship.	Rural	6	10	7	44	13	3.60	1.12
	Urban	8	7	9	37	18	3.66	1.24
Effective classroom management strategies prevent students' punishment.	Rural	2	11	10	36	21	3.79	1.06
	Urban	5	8	8	44	15	3.70	1.09
Effective classroom management makes students socialized.	Rural	3	11	16	39	11	3.54	1.01
	Urban	4	7	9	30	29	3.58	1.17

The table 2 shows that 58% rural & 58% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom management strategies reduce students' distraction. It was revealed from the respondents' response that 59% rural & 52% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that communication is an important component of classroom management. It was indicated from the respondents' response that 57% rural & 56% urban teachers were agreed that communication enables teachers to transfer knowledge. It was found from the respondents' response that 55% rural & 57% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom management enhances students' learning. It was confirmed from the respondents' response that 59% rural & 53% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that Classroom management strategies used for

monitoring. It was shown from the respondents' response that 55% rural & 51% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that good lesson planning is essential for effective teaching.

It was confirmed from the respondents' response that 60% rural & 53% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that questioning is the important device of teaching. It was revealed from the respondents' response that 61% rural & 56% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that classroom management is an appealing environment for students. It was confirmed from the respondents' response that 57% rural & 55% urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom management promotes students' relationship. It was confirmed from the respondents' response 57% rural & 59% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom management strategies prevent students' punishment. It was found from the respondents' response 50% rural & 59% of urban teachers were agreed with the statement that effective classroom management makes students socialized.

Conclusions

It was concluded that the teachers of public secondary schools in central Punjab use classroom management as it is a critical part of effective instruction, helps teacher to teach effectively, feel safe in conducive classroom environment, disciplined classrooms helps teachers to teach well, motivation inspires students to work hard, classroom manager is an efficient teacher, well managed classrooms provide activity based teaching and plays a vital role for teacher success. It was further concluded that teachers of public secondary schools of central Punjab implement classroom management strategies to provide a conducive environment for learning, to solve students' problems, to regulate students' attributes, for effective Communication, provide the productive environment, to reduce student distraction to enhance students' learning and for mentoring process. It was concluded that rural teachers of public secondary school of central Punjab use lesson planning for effective teaching, questioning as the device of classroom management and use classroom management strategies to promote students' relationship, prevent students' punishment and to socialize the students.

It is recommended that this type of research study may be conducted in other provinces of the country to find out the effects of teachers' classroom management strategies at the public secondary level. The research study may also be conducted at the primary and elementary level in Punjab province. The government must increase basic facilities like proper space, electricity, audio video aids for the student. Teachers must be trained in classroom management during induction level or in service training.

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